

Studies on Hydroxamic Acids: Part VIII. Visual Titrations of Hydroxamic Acids in Non-Aqueous Media

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Non-aqueous visual titrations of a wide variety of N-arylhydroxamic acids have been described using cinchophen (2-phenyleinchoninic acid) as a primary standard. The titrations are performed in dimethylformamide and pyridine media using potassium methoxide in benzene-methanol as a titrant and azo violet as an indicator.

Hydroxamic acids represented by the general formula

where R and R' are H, alkyl or aryl radical, are very weak acids. In aqueous medium their pK_a lie between 8 and 10, as such during their titration, satisfactory end points are not observed. Weak acids like phenols have been titrated quite successfully by visual and potentiometric methods in non-aqueous media such as dimethylformamide¹ (DMF), pyridine^{2,3} and ethylenediamine^{1,4} against titrants such as potassium (or sodium) methoxide¹ in benzene-methanol and tetrabutylammonium hydroxide^{2,5} in benzene-methanol (or isopropyl alcohol) with indicators such as azo violet¹ or orthonitraniline¹. In the present study, it is found that hydroxamic acids can be titrated visually in sufficiently protophillic non-aqueous media against highly basic titrants in aprotic solvents with azo violet as an indicator. Both DMF and pyridine have proved to be good solvents for a large number of hydroxamic acids. Cinchophen⁶ (2-phenyleinchoninic acid), $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_2$, has been found to be a suitable primary standard for the standardization of the base titrant, potassium methoxide. It has a distinct advantage over benzoic acid in that it does not form any gelatinous precipitate with alkali metal methoxides. Saturated solution of azo violet (*p*-nitrobenzoazoresorcinol) in anhydrous benzene has been found to be a suitable indicator in these titrations.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus: Magnetic stirrer, vaupet—a rubber device for pipetting liquids by suction and release of air through valves; calibrated apparatus— 5×0.01 ml burette, 10 ml

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2. R. H. Cundiff and P. C. Markunas, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, **28**, 792.
3. M. L. Moss, J. H. Illiot and R. T. Hall, *Anal. Chem.*, 1948, **20**, 784.
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pipette and 100 ml flask; glass tubes (2.5×8.5 cm.; capacity, 25–30 ml) used as titration vessels.

Solvents : Dimethylformamide (A.R., J.T. Baker), methanol (Analar, B.D.H.), benzene (Analar, B.D.H.). These were used without further purification.

Pyridine : Pyridine (L.R., B.D.H.) was purified⁷ by refluxing over sodium hydroxide and then distilling over preheated barium oxide.

Base titrant (0.075–0.1 N) : Metallic potassium, 0.3–0.4 gm., was dissolved, under nitrogen, in minimum quantity of anhydrous methanol and volume made to 100 ml. with anhydrous benzene adding methanol if necessary.

Primary standard, cinchophen : Pharmaceutical grade product was purified by two to three crystallizations from ethanol, m.p. of the purified compound being 217–219°.⁸

Indicator : Saturated solution of azo violet in anhydrous benzene.

Hydroxamic acids : These were obtained as gifts from various workers. Before use these were further purified by crystallization from suitable solvents and were dried in vacuum.

Procedure : A definite amount of the hydroxamic acid (about 0.25 meq.) was dissolved in 10 ml of DMF or pyridine and two drops of the saturated solution of the indicator, azo violet, in anhydrous benzene, were added to it. The solution was stirred with a magnetic stirrer and titrated under a nitrogen blanket, to a green or greenish blue end point against the titrant, potassium methoxide. The solvent blank was subtracted from the observed titre.

The titrant, potassium methoxide, was previously standardised against cinchophen by the same procedure.

Colour changes : As is generally experienced in non-aqueous titrimetry⁹, the indicator passes through several colour changes during the course of titration. Thus, the change of indicator from acid colour to base colour in DMF was from pink red successively to pink orange–orange–green orange–yellow green and finally to green in case of acids, 1–8 (Table I); from red to orange–pink–purple–violet–sky blue–greenish blue in case of acid 9; and from pink to purple–violet–greenish blue (or sky blue) in case of acids, 10–13. The corresponding colour changes of indicator in pyridine medium were identical in case of acids, 1, 8, 9–13; but from red orange to pink–purple–violet–greenish blue (or sky blue) in case of acids, 2,7; and from pink orange to pink–orange–green orange–yellow green–green in case of acids 3–6.

As the solution passes from *yellow green* to *green*, or from *violet* to *greenish blue* (or *sky blue*), at the end point, the latter may be misjudged. To avoid this, the titrations were performed in glass tubes and the colour change was observed horizontally.

7. A. Weissberger, E. S. Proskauer, J. A. Riddic and E. E. Toop, Jr., *Org. Solvents*, Inter Sc. Publishers, Inc., New York, 2nd ed., 1955, p. 446.
8. N. A. Lange, *Hand Book of Chemistry*, McGraw-Hill Book Co., Inc., New York, 10th ed., 1961, p. 657.
9. J. Kucharsky and L. Safarik, *Titrations in Non-Aqueous Solvents*, Elsevier Publishing Co., New York, 1st ed., 1965, p. 115.

The end point was found to be rather indistinct in case of acids such as N-phenylpalmitohydroxamic acid or N-*p*-tolyl-*n*-butyrohydroxamic acid. In such cases, adopting the standard practice⁹, the colour of the indicator at the end point, was ascertained by adding, to the solution, of an accurately weighed amount of the pure acid, two drops of the indicator and an exactly equivalent quantity of the standardized titrant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For titrating a weak acid, the titrant should be as basic as possible, and soluble in an aprotic solvent. Potassium methoxide in 1 : 10 methanol-benzene is highly basic and gives satisfactory end points in the titration of hydroxamic acids. The solvent dissolving the weak acid should also be as protophillic as possible. Both DMF and pyridine are sufficiently protophillic and are good solvents for hydroxamic acids. Ethylenediamine, though more protophillic than DMF or pyridine as a solvent, was found unsuitable because of insufficient solubility of most of the hydroxamic acids in it.

A large number of titrations with a variety of N-arylhydroxamic acids have been performed. Only a few typical results are presented in Table I. Statistical data on titrations are given in Table II. It is observed from these data that the hydroxamic acids can be visually titrated with a fair degree of accuracy.

N-Phenylbeheno- and N-*m*-tolyl-*p*-chlorophenoxyaceto- hydroxamic acids could not be titrated as these were incompletely soluble both in DMF and pyridine. N-Phenyl-3,5-dinitrobenzo- and N-phenyl-*p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acids could also not be titrated as these formed coloured solutions which went on becoming darker on successive additions of the titrant rendering the end point invisible. This behaviour is rather inexplicable especially because their corresponding parent carboxylic acids could be titrated with sharp end points under identical conditions.

Water content of the solvents must not exceed¹⁰ 0.3% otherwise the sensitivity of the end point is affected. Atmospheric carbon dioxide absorbed by basic solvents, pyridine and DMF, is titrated as an acid and interferes with the determination. It also forms the alkali carbonate¹¹ with the alkali methoxide and renders the solution milky. Hence, if the water and carbon dioxide contents of the solvents are kept at a minimum, the accuracy of the visual method attainable¹² in determinations with methoxides using azo violet as an indicator, can be achieved.

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10. *Ibid.*, p. 111.

11. *Ibid.*, p. 117.

12. *Ibid.*, p. 119.

TABLE I
Data on Visual Titration of Hydroxamic Acids

Compd. No.	Hydroxamic Acid	m.p., °C		Amount, gm.	M.wt., Found	M.wt., Calcd.	Error, %
1	N-Phenylbenzo-	Found	121	0.0418	214.2	213.24	+0.45
		Reported, ¹³	121	0.0619	212.8		-0.27
2	N- <i>p</i> -Tolylbenzo-	Found,	110	0.0688	228.3	227.26	+0.46
		Reported, ¹⁴	110	0.0528	226.6		-0.29
3	N- <i>m</i> -Tolylbenzo-	Found,	68-69	0.0572	228.6	227.26	+0.59
		Reported, ¹⁵	70	0.0546	226.2		-0.46
4	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl- <i>p</i> -methylbenzo-	Found,	120-121	0.0576	242.9	241.30	+0.67
		Reported, ¹⁶	119	0.0551	240.2		-0.45
5	N-Phenyl- <i>p</i> -chlorobenzo-	Found,	154	0.0522	249.8	248.70	+0.44
		Reported, ¹⁷	153	0.0612	247.2		-0.59
6	N- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenylbenzo-	Found,	157-158	0.0705	249.9	248.70	+0.48
		Reported, ¹⁸	156-157	0.0682	247.8		-0.36
7	N-Phenyl- <i>o</i> -bromobenzo-	Found,	114-115	0.1522	293.1	292.15	+0.32
		Reported, ¹⁸	113	0.1410	290.6		-0.53
8	N-Phenylcrotono-	Found,	110-111	0.0406	177.4	177.21	+0.11
		Reported, ¹⁹	111	0.0418	176.3		-0.51
9	N-Phenylphenoxyaceto-	Found,	153	0.0742	244.7	243.27	+0.59
		Reported, ¹⁶	154	0.0669	243.1		-0.07
10	N- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-2,4,5-trichlorophenoxyaceto-	Found,	181-182	0.1153	362.3	360.64	+0.46
		Reported, ²⁰	183	0.1060	359.3		-0.37
11	N-Phenyl- <i>n</i> -butyro-	Found,	78-79	0.0458	179.9	179.22	+0.38
		Reported, ²¹	78	0.0519	178.5		-0.40
12	N- <i>i</i> -Tolyl- <i>n</i> -butyro-	Found,	63	0.0509	193.6	193.25	+0.18
		Reported, ¹⁶	63	0.0599	192.9		-0.18
13	N-Phenylpalmito-	Found,	90	0.1048	348.5	347.55	+0.28
		Reported, ¹⁶	91	0.1082	346.1		-0.42

TABLE II
Statistical Data on Determinations of Some Hydroxamic Acids

S.No.	Hydroxamic Acid	No. of observations	Theoretical M.wt.	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation, %
1	N- <i>p</i> -Tolylbenzo-	10	227.255	0.947	0.42
2	N-Phenyl- <i>n</i> -butyro-	5	179.221	0.811	0.45
3	N-Phenyl- <i>p</i> -chlorobenzo-	6	248.696	1.200	0.48

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